

Role of Facebook in Promoting Indian Classical Musicians for Professional Development

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Abstract

In the contemporary digital landscape, the role of social media platforms, particularly Facebook, in promoting professional development among Indian classical musicians is of significant interest. This study investigates the impact of Facebook on Indian classical musicians' careers through a structured questionnaire distributed among practitioners. The research explores two key aspects: firstly, how active engagement on Facebook enhances visibility and promotes networking within the classical music community, and secondly, the platform's effectiveness in broadening audience reach and engagement. Findings reveal widespread Facebook usage among musicians, with a notable positive impact on exposure, networking, and audience expansion. While utilisation of paid advertising features remains low, educational resources on Facebook contribute significantly to professional growth. Overall, Facebook has emerged as an essential tool for Indian classical musicians, facilitating career advancement and networking opportunities in the digital era.

Keywords: Facebook, Indian classical musicians, professional development, social media, audience engagement, networking, digital promotion.

Research Paper

Introduction

In today's world, social media plays a big role in helping people connect and grow. For Indian classical musicians, Facebook is like a stage where they can showcase their talent and build their careers. But how exactly does Facebook help them? That's what this study wants to find out. This study has two major questions to explore. First, this study wants to see how being active on Facebook helps these musicians. Do their posts and interactions on Facebook help them get noticed by other musicians and people who organise concerts? Can Facebook help them make important connections in the music world, like finding people to collaborate with? We're diving into these questions to understand how Facebook helps Indian classical musicians grow their careers through networking. Second, this study enquires about how effective Facebook is in reaching more people. Can Facebook help these musicians share their music with a larger audience? Do more likes and shares on Facebook lead to more chances to perform and get recognised? We want to see if being active on Facebook can help Indian classical musicians reach new heights in their careers. By looking into these questions, this study

is hopeful to learn more about how Facebook supports Indian classical musicians in their professional journey.

In today's digital age, social media has become incredibly popular as a powerful way for people to communicate. It's widely recognized across different areas for encouraging interaction among businesses, groups, communities, and individuals. From companies to social groups, organisations to consumers, social media platforms have become essential for connecting people and fostering engagement. Whether it's sharing ideas, discussing topics, or simply staying in touch, social media has revolutionized how we communicate in the digital era. (Dwivedi, Kapoor and Chen) Platforms like YouTube, social media sites like Facebook, and messaging services such as Twitter help artists connect with fans and grow their audience. Nowadays, artists can also work together with companies in different entertainment fields like games, movies, and TV shows, which can create new ways for them to earn money by partnering with advertisers. (Tschmuck) Among the variety of Social Network Sites [SNS], Facebook is one of the most popular SNSs used to connect and interact with contacts (Ellison).

classical music and the increasing influence of digital platforms, understanding how Facebook contributes to the professional growth of musicians in this genre is crucial. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating the impact of Facebook on Indian classical musicians' careers, shedding light on its effectiveness in enhancing visibility, networking opportunities, and audience reach within the classical music community. By examining the usage patterns and perceptions of musicians regarding Facebook, this research seeks to provide valuable insights into the evolving dynamics of music promotion and career advancement in the digital age.

Research Problem

Investigating the role of Facebook in supporting Indian classical musicians' careers involves examining two crucial aspects. Firstly, we seek to understand how active engagement with Facebook aids these musicians in their professional journey. This involves evaluating whether their presence on Facebook enhances their visibility within the classical music community. Through regular updates and interactions on the platform, are they able to attract attention from fellow musicians, concert organizers, and industry professionals? Furthermore, does Facebook serve as a platform for building meaningful connections and friendships within the industry, potentially leading to collaboration opportunities and performance invitations? By delving into these questions, we aim to gain insights into how Facebook facilitates networking and career growth for Indian classical musicians.

Secondly, we aim to assess the effectiveness of Facebook in broadening the audience reach and engagement of Indian classical musicians. We explore whether Facebook serves as an effective tool for reaching a larger audience and sparking interest in classical music among diverse listeners. Do Indian classical musicians perceive Facebook as a platform capable of amplifying their music to a broader audience base? Additionally, we investigate how increased exposure and engagement on Facebook translate into tangible benefits for their careers. Does greater visibility and engagement on Facebook lead to more performance opportunities, increased recognition, and overall career advancement for Indian classical musicians?

Hypothesis

Being active on Facebook greatly affects the careers of Indian classical musicians. It helps them get noticed more by other musicians, concert planners, and people

in the music industry. Plus, it's a great way for them to make friends and work with other musicians.

Facebook also helps these musicians reach more people who might be interested in classical music. More people seeing their posts and videos means more chances for them to perform and get recognized.

Relevance of the Study

The research on the role of Facebook in promoting Indian classical musicians for professional development offers straightforward insights that can greatly benefit musicians in their careers. By understanding how Facebook can enhance their visibility and networking opportunities, musicians gain valuable knowledge on how to effectively utilize social media platforms to advance their careers. The findings provide practical guidance on posting frequency, content types, and engagement strategies that can help musicians attract attention from peers, concert organizers, and industry professionals. Moreover, the research highlights the potential for collaboration and performance opportunities that Facebook offers within the classical music community. Musicians can use this information to build meaningful connections, explore new avenues for growth, and expand their audience reach. Additionally, by showcasing the availability of educational resources and training opportunities on Facebook, the research encourages musicians to engage with online learning platforms to further develop their skills and expertise. Overall, this research empowers Indian classical musicians with actionable insights that can help them navigate the digital landscape, promote their artistry, and pursue their professional aspirations with confidence.

Research Methodology

The methodology adopted for investigating the overall role of Facebook in promoting Indian classical musicians for professional development involved several systematic steps aimed at collecting and analysing relevant data. Initially, a literature review was conducted to explore existing research articles and works related to the role of social media platforms, particularly Facebook, in promoting musicians' careers. This preliminary review helped identify the research area and frame major research questions pertinent to the study.

Following the identification of the research questions, a structured questionnaire consisting of 24 questions was developed using Google Forms. The questionnaire was designed to gather broad insights into various aspects

Facebook holds a prominent position as one of the leading social networking platforms worldwide. What's noteworthy is its widespread appeal across different age demographics. Particularly, it has gained considerable traction among the younger generation, who constitute a significant portion of its user community. This broad acceptance and usage among users of varying ages underscore Facebook's pervasive influence in today's digital landscape. (Thapa)

In 2014, Facebook became a huge social media network that made it simple for people with similar interests to connect. It offered features like sharing information, videos, music, and chatting, either instantly or at different times, which was perfect for groups to interact and learn together. This made it an ideal place for communities to come together and share their knowledge and experiences. (Barnes) Facebook's various features are also being used to inspire customers to engage with organizations and encourage them to create value together. (Marandi)

In Facebook groups, people do various activities based on what the group is about or what interests them individually. (Lutzu)

For the past thirty years, music lovers have been using the internet to connect and share their passion for music. They gather on digital platforms to chat, make friends, and show support for their favourite artists. But back then, the artists themselves weren't part of these online discussions. They were usually busy performing live or appearing in traditional media like TV and radio. So, when fans started chatting online, the music industry didn't pay much attention. They thought it was just a small, niche hobby, not something important. (Baym) The rise of digital technology has shifted the focus to artists, making them more important in the music industry. (Tschmuck) In the past ten years, promoting music has changed a lot because of social media. Nowadays, it's not just a choice for musicians to use social media – it's really important for their careers. Platforms like Facebook have become super popular among musicians because they let them connect with fans, share their music, and grow their careers. As musicians deal with all the challenges of the music industry today, having a good social media presence is key. (Baym)

People who use Facebook usually spend their time on the platform to stay in touch with friends and organizations, share pictures, and use different apps. (A.N. Joinson) Before the rise of the internet, artists relied on music publishers and record labels to share their music with the

world. This meant they had to permit these companies to distribute their music. Because these publishers and labels were often part of the same big record companies, they demanded full control over the music through exclusive licenses from the artists. (Tschmuck) The digital transformation in the music world hasn't only altered how music gets shared but has also completely changed how it's valued and distributed. Businesses that weren't previously connected, or only had limited connections to the music scene, have now become crucial players in it. (Tschmuck) New technologies are like a big gift for musicians, especially those who work on their own. People believed that these new ideas would help musicians advertise their music, talk directly to their fans, and sell their stuff alongside famous singers online. This meant they wouldn't have to rely on big music companies as much. (Marshall)

As more and more music-sharing and streaming services pop up online, personalized music is becoming increasingly important to many people. This rise goes hand in hand with a growing curiosity about why we like certain types of music. (Gideon Nave) Sharing things like news, videos, and articles on social media has become really common. It gives people a way to connect with others and be part of what's happening in the world. (Benjamin K. Johnson)

Social media provides valuable information about customers. People freely share their preferences for brands, products, services, and more on social platforms. By gathering this data from potential customers, such as those interested in a specific company, businesses can create detailed online profiles. These profiles help target individuals more effectively with personalized marketing. (Jan-Willem van Dam) So, getting music out there on digital platforms is becoming more and more crucial. It allows artists to break free from relying solely on record labels. (Tschmuck) Because of the digital revolution, artists now rely less on traditional music industry methods. Many bands and individual musicians started sharing their music directly on the internet. (Tschmuck)

Background of the Study

In the modern era, social media platforms have become integral to various aspects of life, including professional development. Among these platforms, Facebook holds a prominent position as a tool for networking, promotion, and engagement. However, its specific role in promoting the careers of Indian classical musicians remains relatively underexplored. With the rich tradition of Indian

of musicians' engagement with Facebook, including their usage patterns, supposed impact on professional development, and experiences with networking and promotional activities on the platform. The questionnaire was categorized into sections covering Personal Information, Demographics, Music Career Details, Facebook Usage, Impact of Facebook, and Additional Comments, to facilitate organized data collection.

To reach out to the target population, which comprised Indian classical musicians, the questionnaire was distributed through various communication channels such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Messenger, and Email. Musicians were invited to participate in the survey voluntarily, and efforts were made to ensure broad representation across different age groups, genders, and career stages within the Indian classical music community.

After receiving responses from the participants, the data were scrutinised, cleaned, compiled and organized using Microsoft Excel for further analysis. A total of 58 counts of responses were selected for analysis. Pivot tables were used to summarize and disaggregate the collected data, allowing for the extraction of meaningful insights and patterns. Additionally, tables and charts were generated to present the findings in a structured and visually appealing manner, facilitating easier interpretation and comparison of results.

The methodology used in this study was integrated towards systematically collecting and analysing empirical data to investigate how Facebook contributes to the professional development of Indian classical musicians. Through the use of a structured questionnaire and analytical tools, the research aimed to offer thorough insights into the usage patterns and the perceived influence of Facebook on the careers of Indian classical musicians.

Result

The analysis was conducted on a count of 58 respondents. In the realm of Indian classical music, the youth demographic dominates Facebook usage, suggesting its relevance among younger musicians. [Table – 1, Table-1]

Table: 1

Facebook Usage	Female	Male	Grand Total
No	3	4	7
Yes	21	30	51
Grand Total	24	34	58

Chart: 1
Facebook Usage

Additionally, a significant proportion of male Indian classical musicians actively utilize Facebook, indicating its popularity as a platform for self-promotion within the community. When considering the duration of their careers, the majority of musicians have been engaged in Indian classical music for 10 to 15 years, followed by those with less than 10 years of experience and those with 16 to 30 years of experience. This diversity in experience levels showcases Facebook's adoption across different career stages. Furthermore, vocalists constitute the majority of specialization among Indian classical musicians, aligning with the nature of content shared on Facebook, such as performance videos.

The impact of Facebook on Indian classical musicians' careers is significant, with a resounding acknowledgement of its role in exposure and networking. A staggering 83% of respondents attribute Facebook to aiding them in gaining exposure and reaching a wider audience, underscoring its importance in career advancement [Table – 2, Table - 2].

Table: 2

Gaining Exposure	Female	Male	Grand Total
No	4	10	14
Yes	20	24	44
Grand Total	24	34	58

Chart: 2
Gaining Exposure

Moreover, three-fourths of musicians have received performance opportunities or collaborations through Facebook, highlighting its potential as a networking platform within the Indian classical music field [Table - 3, Table - 3].

Table: 3

Performances Opportunities	Female	Male	Grand Total
No	9	12	21
Yes	15	22	37
Grand Total	24	34	58

Chart: 3

Networking on Facebook has positively impacted professional development for many musicians, with 17% reporting it as significantly good and 42% as good [Table - 4, Table - 4].

Table: 4

Networking Impact	Female	Male	Grand Total
Average	8	15	23
good	10	11	21
Not at all	2	2	4
Significantly good	4	6	10
Grand Total	24	34	58

Chart: 4

However, the utilization of Facebook's paid advertising or sponsored post features remains relatively low, with only 4% of musicians employing these tools. Among those who have used paid advertising, opinions on its effectiveness are mixed, suggesting room for improvement or varying strategies. Nevertheless, educational resources, workshops, or training opportunities related to Indian classical music are readily available on Facebook, with 75% of musicians encountering such resources. Among those who accessed educational resources, 44% found them contributing to their professional growth as Indian classical musicians.

Overall, the majority perceive Facebook's impact on professional development positively, indicating its importance in supporting classical musicians' careers. Ratings suggest varying degrees of impact, with a significant portion acknowledging substantial influence [Table - 5, Table - 5].

Table: 5

Overall Impact Scale	Rating Count
1	2
2	4
3	28
4	14
5	10
Grand Total	58

Chart: 5

This collective understanding underscores the significant role of Facebook in fostering the professional growth of Indian classical musicians in the digital age.

Discussion

Based on the responses gathered from the questionnaire, several key findings emerge regarding the role of Facebook in promoting Indian classical musicians for professional development. Firstly, it is evident that the youth demographic dominates Facebook participation

within the Indian classical music community, comprising two-thirds of the total users. Additionally, a significant proportion of male Indian classical musicians, accounting for nearly 59%, utilize Facebook as a platform to promote their music careers. When considering the duration of their careers, the majority of musicians have been engaged in Indian classical music for 10 to 15 years, followed by those with less than 10 years of experience and those with 16 to 30 years of experience.

Regarding specialization, vocalists constitute the majority at 88%, while instrumentalists represent 12% of the surveyed population. An overwhelming 88% of musicians actively use Facebook to promote their Indian classical music careers, demonstrating the platform's widespread adoption within the community. In terms of posting frequency, a significant portion of musicians (71%) post music-related updates occasionally, followed by a few times a week (21%). Performance videos emerge as the most commonly shared content type at 71%, followed by concert updates (21%) and teaching content (8%).

Facebook's impact on exposure and audience reach for Indian classical musicians is notable, with 83% of respondents acknowledging its role in helping them gain exposure and reach a wider audience. Moreover, three-fourths of musicians have received performance opportunities or collaborations through Facebook, indicating its significance as a networking platform within the Indian classical music field. Networking on Facebook has positively impacted professional development for many musicians, with 17% reporting it as significantly good and 42% as good.

However, the utilization of Facebook's paid advertising or sponsored post features remains relatively low, with only 4% of musicians employing these tools. Among those who have used paid advertising, opinions on its effectiveness are divided, with 38% finding it effective and another 38% considering it not effective. Despite this, a majority (71%) of musicians reported a potential increase in followers or engagement after using paid advertising or sponsored posts.

Furthermore, educational resources, workshops, or training opportunities related to Indian classical music are readily available on Facebook, with 75% of musicians encountering such resources. Among those who accessed educational resources, 44% found them contributing to their professional growth as Indian

classical musicians. Overall, Facebook's impact on professional development is perceived positively by the majority, with 48% rating it as 3, followed by 24% as 4, and 17% as 5 on a scale of 1 to 5. These findings collectively highlight the significant role of Facebook in supporting Indian classical musicians' careers and fostering their professional growth in the digital age.'

Conclusion

In summary, this research looked at how Facebook helps Indian classical musicians in their careers. We found that many musicians, especially young ones, use Facebook a lot. It's a big help for them to get noticed and connect with others in the music world. Facebook also helps them reach more people who might like their music. Even though not many musicians use Facebook ads, it still makes a difference in getting more followers and engagement. Plus, there are lots of useful resources and training available on Facebook for musicians to learn and grow. Overall, Facebook plays a vital role in helping Indian classical musicians build their careers in today's digital world.

Appendix: List of participants who participated in the study

Abhishek Bhunia, Aishwarya Chakraborty, Amit Chatterjee, Anal Chatterjee, Angshubha Banerjee, Ankita Datta, Ankita Purkayastha, Anumita Sengupta, Anushka Dan, Arjayeeta Paul, Avanti Ganeshrao Sakhale, Babloo Kumar [Ketan], Biswajit Nandi, Biswajit Pal, Debashish Singha Roy, Debabrata Chowdhury, Dipanwita Mukherjee, Dr Aniruddh Kumar Singh, Dr Siddhartha Choudhury, Dr Sumona Banerjee, Dr. Sandeep Kumar Patel, Dr. Krishnendu Dutta, Hindol Sarkar, Hindol Sarkar, Jagannath Barman, Karanika Dey, Kathika Kushari, Madhusudan Laha, Mayurakshi Biswas, Mita Nag, Mohana Chakraborty, Mohit Kr Mehta, Monit Paul, Ms Aditi Singla, Padma Palas Halder, Pankaj Kumar Barman, Parimal Chakraborty, Poushali Ghosh, Pranav Nanoti, Prof Tapasi Ghosh, Rageshree Das Choudhury, Ram Jondhale, Rosy Dutta, Sagnik Bhattacharya, Sameer Thamke, Sanghamitra Chakraborty, Santosh Kumar, Shrabanika Changmai, Sounak Chattopadhyay, Srinidhi Chakravartula, Sumana Chakraborty, Supratik Sengupta, Sushmita Das, T Datta, Tanishq Vishwakarma, Ujjwal Bharati, Utathya Kalita.

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